

José F Papí

Sustainability: green is the new black

Transportation networks must satisfy high mobility demands, but at the same time must do it with the lowest possible energy consumption and CO2 emissions. At the same time, plenty of innovative 'recipes' are available, even if their market uptake has been quite limited to date.

Solutions to improve infrastructure energy efficiency include the reduction of the energy embodied in the physical structures through re-use and recycling, the implementation of low energy systems and energy harvesting from the infrastructure itself to the extent of self-sufficient production. In addition, infrastructure design, maintenance and operation can have a substantial influence on the energy consumed by the vehicles, vessels and aircrafts operating on it.

I would also highlight that a better integration of infrastructure in its natural habitat (avoiding fragmentation as much as possible), together with a reduced intrusion of noise, air pollution and vibration, is an ethical responsibility for our modern societies.

Dedicated 'green corridors' using new types of vehicles over medium distances are one of my favourite solutions (please take a look at this great idea: www.tevproject.com), as I am not so convinced the market potential (or even the technological viability) of safe automated driving for day-to-day commuter mobility will be realised in the short and medium-term.

Last but not least, infrastructure cannot forget to support the soft modes of transport (e.g. cycling and walking) and must supply a sustainable and cross-modal urban transport ecosystem.

SUSTAINABLE ALL THE WAY

Parameters such as the durability and the re-use and recycling of materials are becoming more relevant in an economic context that demands higher efficiency. At the same time, innovative systems and processes for construction are key to improve sustainability of transportation infrastructures worldwide.

Long-lasting, climate-resilient and more environmentally aware construction materials are also having a growing role in the construction of new corridors and hubs, together with cost-efficient and fast design methods. Self-healing and self-cleaning technologies (e.g. applied to coatings, pavements or bridges) will

also enhance faster and better-planned quality control systems.

TOWARDS CLIMATE-RESILIENT INFRASTRUCTURES

Climate stresses in the recent past involve changes in temperature, precipitation, storm activity, sea level, wind speeds and more. These effects can in turn lead to impacts on transportation infrastructure, such as weakened bridges and road beds, expanded rail tracks, delays and disruption in ports due to sea levels rise or damaged airstrips.

The effects of climate change are real: transportation infrastructure is not always ready to cope with extreme weather conditions, which result in an extra cost to transportation infrastructures. Climate change impacts can be revealed as major incidents that occur more often, or as small and incremental changes that over the years deteriorate and erode the quality of transportation infrastructures.

Adaptation of infrastructure to climate requires taking in account every stage of the infrastructure management process: planning, design, construction, operation and maintenance. Easier said than done, but understanding and proactively addressing the potential impacts of climate stresses can help avoiding the potential damage, disruption in service, and safety concerns that may emerge.

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